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Research Article

**A FOCUSED ENDOTHERMIC RESPONSE TEST FOR
VEERYA'S AMALAKI SURVEY**¹Dr Sufyan Ali, ²Dr Ali Hassan, ³Dr Muhammad Salik¹Punjab Medical College Faisalabad²Doctors Hospital and Medical Center Lahore³BHU Bharoke Cheema, Gujranwala**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Ayurveda mainly manages two kinds of veerya (power). The first is sheeta (cold) and the second is ushna (hot). The treatment modalities of Ayurveda depend on Rasapanchak. Thus, the veerya (strength) of medicines plays an indispensable role in the standards of treatment. Thus, the examination of the strength of exothermic and endothermic responses of the medicines requires some groundwork. Various market tests show that adulterants are more effective than single old-fashioned drugs, or that if restorative endogenous plants appear, other substitute drugs are used. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2018 to April 2019. It is therefore essential to remedy these shortcomings by carrying out an Ayurvedic examination of these tests.

Keywords: Focused, Endothermic Response, Test, Veerya's Amalaki Survey.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Sufyan Ali,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Many synthetic responses discharge vitality in the form of heat, light or sound [1]. These are exothermic responses. Exothermic responses can occur suddenly and cause arbitrariness or higher entropy. ($\Delta S > 0$) of the frame [2]. They are indicated by a negative heat flow (heat is lost to the environment) and a reduction in enthalpy ($\Delta H < 0$). In the laboratory, exothermic responses produce heat or may even be unstable. There are other concoction responses that must assimilate vitality to continue. These are the endothermic responses [3]. Endothermic responses cannot occur unexpectedly. You have to work to make these responses happen. When the endothermic responses ingest vitality, it is estimated that there is a drop in temperature during the response [4]. Endothermic responses are described by a positive heat flow (in the response) and an expansion of enthalpy ($+\Delta H$) [5].

METHODOLOGY:

Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2018 to April 2019. It is therefore essential to remedy these shortcomings by carrying out an Ayurvedic examination of these tests.

Examples of endothermic and exothermic processes:

Photosynthesis is a case of endothermic concoction response. For now, use the vitality of the sun to convert carbon dioxide and water into glucose and oxygen. This reaction requires 15MJ of vitality (daylight) for each kilogram of glucose created: daylight + $6\text{CO}_2(\text{g}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l}) = \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6(\text{aq}) + 6\text{O}_2(\text{g})$

A case of exothermic response is the mixing of sodium and chlorine to produce table salt. This response produces 411 kJ of vitality for each mole of salt that is delivered: $\text{Na}(\text{s}) + 0.5\text{Cl}_2(\text{s}) = \text{NaCl}(\text{s})$

Demonstrations You Can Perform:

Among the many exothermic and endothermic responses are harmful synthetic substances, extraordinary heat or cold, or chaotic disposal techniques. These are protected and easy.1

Materials and strategies:**Exothermic response for the veerya test:****RESULTS:**

10 ml of water taken from a measuring cup and the temperature was noted repeatedly, at this point 10 grams of Amalaki churma are included in the water and temperature changes were noted after 1 moment, 3 minutes and 7 minutes and 60 minutes.

Table No.1: Endothermic reaction of Embolic officinalis Gaertner.

Media			Duration		
Water	Water	Water	After 1 minute (Emblica officinalis Gaertn.)	After 3 minutes (Emblica officinalis Gaertn.)	After 5 minutes (Emblica officinalis Gaertn.)
75.6of	75.6of	75.6of	75.00f	74.80f	74.80f

Image 1: After 1 minute

Image 2: After 3 minutes

Image 3: After 5 minutes

Result and Conclusion:

Based on the above, the result is unequivocally Amalaka (Embolic officinalis Gaertner.) while Sheet veerya dravya demonstrated an endothermic response. In addition, the temperature increased by 0.3 to 20 C.

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